

**APPRAISING TEACHING METHODS FOR QUALITATIVE SOCIAL STUDIES
IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

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Abstract

This paper explored teaching methods and qualitative Social Studies in Nigeria. It discussed Social Studies as a discipline and examined its teaching methods. Furthermore, ways forward for developing qualitative Social Studies through the use of effective teaching methods were explored. The paper made use of library research through which previous works were reviewed in books, journal articles, newspapers and the Internet. The paper suggested that Social Studies as a discipline in Nigeria contributes greatly to the maintenance of unity in diversity among the people. It also found that although there were many teaching methods in use in Social Studies classrooms, no one method was found to be the best as the eclectic approach was recommended because of the complex nature of the subject. The study concluded that the knowledge of methods was central to Social Studies' pedagogy. Various stakeholders were enjoined by the paper to work on it.

Keywords: Teaching methods; Qualitative education; Social Studies; Conventional methods

Introduction

Social Studies is an integrative discipline that studies man in his habitat which includes social, political, economic and physical environments. It covers the complex relationships of man with the environment. Therefore, it requires the use of diverse teaching methods to communicate diverse issues that emanate from the human environment. The quest for qualitative education has become one of the major themes in educational enterprise in Nigeria. This, perhaps, is because of the poor performance in schools in recent times. Scholars have agreed that there is a need to attain qualitative education in Nigeria to ensure sustainable socio-economic development, global recognition and individual ability to service in the contemporary environment (Ahimode, 2013). Ahimode (2013) examined the ways to integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the Nigerian educational system to enhance quality. The paper further identified some impediments to quality education in Nigeria to include poor school attendance, lack of effective classroom control and the inability to ensure equitable education across gender, ethnic and regional lines.

A careful consideration of the observation points to the fact that there is a need to develop students' interest in education through the use of dynamic and interactive

teaching methods, effective classroom presentation and management. This forms a substantial portion in the quest to improve quality education.

This paper focuses on the examination of teaching methods to ensure the enhancement of quality education in Social Studies. The paper has the following objectives:

- (a) examine the concept of qualitative education
- (b) discuss the discipline of Social Studies in the educational system in Nigeria;
- (c) examine teaching methods in Social Studies; and
- (d) identify ways forward for developing qualitative Social Studies through teaching methods.

Concept of Qualitative Education

According to Chukwu (2015), a qualitative education is delivered in a school in which the curriculum delivery is learner-centred and promotes active participation of the pupils. Teachers possess the knowledge, skills and abilities for the mastery of the contents and skills and the learning environment is conducive. He further observes that in such school, teachers accept accountability for students' academic performance and their rights are protected. Furthermore, the classroom must be orderly and disciplined while the environment is conducive.

The quality of teaching determines student performance. In other to develop teaching quality, the teacher must be skilled in lesson plan, take into account the students' needs and attract students' interest to ensure readiness in the classroom (Chukwu, 2015; Salawudeen, 2020). The quality of teaching also depends on teachers' skills in communication, understanding of the content and the use of appropriate teaching methodologies.

Miles and Frank (2008) cited in Chukwu (2015) propose that schools should acquire the following: qualitative staffing with adequate skills and professionalism, adequate with scheduling to collaborate with other school personnel for effective delivery and, build a system that promotes effective teaching and motivation through induction. These will ensure the achievement of the objectives of development planning, evaluation and the school curriculum objectives through improved academic service delivery. They further identified strategies to ensure qualitative teaching and improve school performance. These are: the determination of academic needs; assessment of school resources for meeting academic needs and setting concrete goals for the school's teaching quality needs. These goals must be attainable and devoted to the realisation of the already identified academic needs.

This paper proposes to examine teaching methods in Social Studies as a way of ensuring teachers' classroom delivery and qualitative education. This has become more important for Social Studies with its multidisciplinary approach.

Evolution of Social Studies as a Discipline

Social Studies was introduced to Nigeria in 1958 by scholars from Ohio University Project who introduced it to Teachers' Colleges in Western Nigeria (Unimna, Essien, Effion & Godwin, 2020). The early introduction was not successful because there was no preparation then for its implementation. Existing schools did not have the subject

in their curricula and there were no local teachers to complement the efforts of the pioneers (Amos, 2014; Unimna, *et al* 2020).

The subject was introduced the second time in Nigeria through the Comprehensive High School Ayetoro, Egbado. The institution was established to model a comprehensive secondary education in Nigeria (Amos, 2014). The school commenced the teaching of the subject 1963. Prior to this time, Nigeria's Independence in 1960 had developed the interest of Nigerian educators in curriculum reforms which was designed to aid self-discovery to reverse the debilitating outcomes of colonial education on Nigerians, (Famwang, 2000; Unimna, *et al* 2020).

At the Comprehensive High School, Ayetoro, Egbado, the school developed curriculum in subjects which include Mathematics, Social Studies, Integrated Science, Technical Education and Home Economics between 1963 and 1968 (Amos, 2014). The school produced the first book on Social Studies course for the first two years of the then five-year secondary school. To determine the aims and objectives of the course were not easy because of its complexity. The Western Region Ministry of Education in 1965 assisted to come up with this, later. According to Makinde (1979), cited in Adewuya (1992), these include:

- a) making Nigerians comprehend their physical, social and cultural environments;
- b) developing, encouraging and strengthening enquiring minds so as to assist students to rediscover themselves.

The above formed the basis for secondary school Social Studies in Nigeria. The importance of the subject then was to:

- i. foster unity and nationalization of Nigerians and its people;
- ii. help students to cultivate problem solving skills through exposure;
- iii. develop positive values and attitudes, and
- iv. cultivate democratic values.

Although the draft was done in 1967 and experimented in Ayetoro, its final version was not ready for use until April, 24th to May 4th, 1968 when the educator(s) conference came up in the University of Lagos. The conference critiqued its objectives, content selection and inter-disciplinary approach (Unimna, *et al*, 2020). Another significant outcome of the conference was the decision on the teaching methodology for Social Studies. These methods departed significantly from the conventional lecture method and emphasized the use of inductive or deductive methods of teaching (Adewuya, 1992). This was, perhaps meant, to encourage classroom participation and make the subject more real and thought provoking.

There was a Feedback Conference in Ayetoro in April, 1970 by the earlier inducted teachers who were exposed to basic skills in Social Studies teaching methodology. It also obtained feedback from them on the relevance of the textbooks prepared by the experts with a view to improving teacher capability at handling Social Studies at that level. Since then, the discipline of Social Studies has contributed to national development.

Fadeiye, (2005) saw Social Studies as a problem-solving discipline especially in a country like Nigeria where social problems arise as a result of modernity which is fast replacing old norms and values.

Having considered various definitions from scholars, the National Council for Social Studies (1994) defined it as a wholistic study of social sciences and humanities to promote civic competence. From this definition, it has been argued that Social Studies is an issue-focused and inquiry-based interdisciplinary subject which provides opportunities for students to acquire the knowledge and skills and develop the attitudes necessary for them to become responsible citizens needed in multi-cultural and democratic society like Nigeria (Ukadike, 2010). It has also been contended by Ogunyemi (2008) that the dynamic nature of the subject makes it to respond to the various emerging social problems such as democracy, human right, good governance, environment and population. Components of Social Studies are citizenship education, population education, gender issue, and environmental education among others.

Methods of Teaching Social Studies

Given the nature of the subject, it is incumbent upon teachers to consider the subjects, classroom size and students' characteristics before choosing a method. According to Adejumobi (1981) cited in Akintola (2001), problems relating to the Social Studies classroom situation include: the problems of inadequate methods; absence of well – equipped libraries in most of the schools; inadequate textbooks and reference books; lack of adequate funds for excursions and field trips and lack of suitable teaching aids. In deciding on the methods, the above problems need to be taken into consideration.

Presentation Method

This is a traditional form of classroom interaction. Teaching under this method is viewed as presentation of ideas and information through verbal communication (Akintola, 2001). Perhaps, the major problems of this method include little personal interaction between pupils and the teacher and lack of direct communication between the pupils and the teacher. Thus, in using this method, teachers must exercise adequate skill and care so that their effectiveness can be maximized (Akintola, 2001; Omotuyole and Manuel, 2014). For the pupils to pay attention, their presentation must be interesting and backed up with adequate teaching resources.

Inquiry or Discovery Method

This is one of the key methods of teaching Social Studies because it helps students to develop curious, imaginable and critical thinking faculties required for independent learning. Bickers (2020) opines that the method identifies a problem, analyses of information for problem solving and generalises the solution to solve future novel problems. The subject stresses student's familiarity with the physical and social environments, improves social skills and values; promotes abilities be rational, critically, creative and independent which are related to problem solving (Okogu, 2013). This method has been successfully used in the Social Studies teaching (Obadiora, 2009, Okogu, 2013).

Project Method

This is another conventional method which has been suggested for the teaching of Social Studies (Okogu, 2013; Farmson, 2020). This is a method which an individual or

a group of students could use by co-operation between, or among themselves. It makes use of self-motivation and ideas. It also requires the teacher to plan with the aim of getting students to make use of information for successful learning encounter. Okogu (2013) has suggested that project method can be successfully used in Social Studies in the areas of group story writing and interpretation and making maps; and so on. However, it has been noted that a project should take into consideration the ability levels of the students (Farmson, 2020; Salawudeen, 2019).

Creative Activity Method

It is another method which involves learning the development of creative as well as cognitive abilities (Farmson, 2020; Gimba, Gimba & Saguna 2019). In creative activity method, the teacher should organize, assist and help, but to be really creative, the activities must be done by the students. However, the researchers observed that in using the method, the teacher should be careful so as not to become too competitive or critical. Pupil's work should not excessively be criticized as one would do for an adult's work. Also, teachers must be careful that the activities refer to something in the syllabus and are not just time filling.

Discussion Method

It focuses on the cognition of the pupils. It is a thinking together process or a type of cooperation in learning that requires team-work among the learners (Mbah, 2018). The discussion method is a peer group tutoring method with some intervention from the teacher. It makes use of a small group with a leader who initiates the discussion of the topic. In the use of this method, students take active role, while the teacher merely facilitates the learning outcome. Therefore, the method may be more appropriate where students' readiness and motivation are high. However, the teacher should be cautious of overly domination of the classroom by some students. Each and every classroom participant should be allowed to make their own contribution (Mbah, 2018). The discussion method has been suggested to be appropriate in teaching Social Studies, relating to man's social environment (Mbah, 2018). In using the method, there is need for deliberate planning with the teacher guiding and molding slow learners' discussions.

Lecture Method

In Social Studies, lecture method has also been found to be common (Farmson, 2020). The assumption of this method is that the students will be passive in the classroom. In most cases, however, the lecture may conclude with a teacher's summary and some questions. However, the use of lecture method becomes imperative when the topic is abstract. Edeh, Ezegbe, Onwurah, Dike & Uzodinma (2018) observe that such abstract topics in Social Studies include; "faith; reason, man and his beliefs; supernaturalism, justice" and so on. In addition, the method is appropriate for a large classroom or where there is a shortage of accommodation and personnel. But the major disadvantage of this method is that the teacher is at the centre of the learning. Rather than encouraging students' participation, it dishes out information to them. Also, a lesson under this method requires the combination with other methods and the use of instructional aids (Egbarevba & Iyamu, 2020).

Dramatization Method

This is a method to stimulate students to learn. It allows students' participation and involvement in classroom activities. Farmson, (2020), identifies dramatization as one of the most effective for stimulating and interesting pupils. Its techniques include miming, role-playing and playlet which are especially useful in primary classes. In a descriptive study reported by Megahed and Al-Dakomy (2023) in Egypt, it was affirmed that dramatization method was very effective in imparting Social Studies learning in the classroom. Its major advantage is that it attracts pupils' attention and arouse their interest in the subject. It has the capacity of promoting classroom participation of all categories of learners. The opportunity to interact and play will ensure classroom participation and enhances feedback. Adequate preparation must be made to allow students to master their roles. Students can be made to perform varying roles in the family such as the father and the mother or the children; act to show the virtues of honesty, leadership and followership among others.

Construction Method

It is a method which helps the students to learn by doing and embark on self-directed activities. These activities have identified to be of two kinds (Farmson, 2020). The first is made of print materials which include magazine and book. The second one involves the use of items like sculptures, and models. In using this method, teachers must initiate the construction method. This technique has been identified to be useful in teaching the family structure, the systems of government, social obligations, cultural patterns and so on in Social Studies. The instructor must follow adequate safety precaution if process includes the use of sharp objects to avoid sustaining injuries.

Contract Activity Instructional Strategy

Contract Activity Instructional Strategy (CAIS) is originated as Contract Activity Package (CAP) by Rita Dunn and Kenneth Dunn (Boyle; Russo & Lefkowitz 2008). In this paper, both terms are synonymous with the concept of individualized teaching developed by the above scholars. The CAIS is a pedagogical method which allows students to learn at their own pace. Students can make use of CAIS as individual, with another participant or two or as a part of a team through small group activities. It is most effective with independent and motivated participants because they provide self-pacing for individuals who want to achieve, improve or be among the best in their field. Thus, CAIS promotes independent and individualized learning. It is designed in such a way that it can improve learning in teams. Studies have found that CAIS is so flexible that students can work with it to maximize their capacities for "concentrating and producing." They may embark on self-adjustment for light, temperature and design to match their learning styles (Boyle, Russo & Lefkowitz 2002). CAIS has been found effective in improving academic performance and retention (Salawudeen, 2019).

Developing Qualitative Social Studies Education through Innovative Teaching Methods

Social Studies deals with people, their attitudes, beliefs and values and their interaction with themselves and their environment. Therefore, the Social Studies teacher

owes it a duty to approach the subject, taking into consideration the human nature and problems (Ajitoni; Salako & Oyedepo, 2012). He has to develop an open and critical mind which is prepared to encourage a free expression of others' point of view and disagreements.

In a study conducted to analyse patterns of interaction that occur in junior secondary school Social Studies classrooms, Falaye (2007) found that teachers dominated in all classes with significant proportion of the time devoted to giving facts about the subject content. He noted further that very little attention was given to the social-emotional climate that prevailed in the classroom. These findings lend credence to earlier studies on the subject matter (Amos, 2014). It was found that the social-emotional capabilities of the pupils could not be nurtured in an atmosphere when there is no diversity and interdependence among people in the society. Egbarevba & Iyamu (2014) explored the effective ways of teaching Social Studies in schools. They found that apart from other parameters like the availability of teaching materials, teaching methods adopted were central.

Teaching of Social Studies therefore, entails a full understanding of the appropriate methods to achieve the objectives as stated by the National Policy on Education. Teaching methods are the principles and strategies of instruction. According to Adekunle (2010), teaching involves interaction with one another to influence and evolve learning between the teacher and the learners which involves the use of intuition, creativity, improvisation and expressiveness. Therefore, teaching method involves all those techniques, procedures, manipulations and facilitation of content and learning environments that are performed by the teachers (Obadiora, 2009; Megahed & Al-Dakomy, 2023). Furthermore, teaching method includes any technique or strategy employed by a teacher while transmitting knowledge, skills and values to students to ensure a proper understanding of the lesson. Perhaps because of the importance of teaching methods in teaching and learning encounters, teachers must be able to communicate the content effectively. Thus, effective communication in teaching and learning situation requires clear presentation of the subject content in a language that the students can understand (Raw & Reddy, 1992 cited in Obadiora, 2009).

Selecting an appropriate method in teaching Social Studies is not an easy task. This is partly because the focus of the subject is man and his diverse interactions with the environment. In order to teach Social Studies, therefore, a teacher must possess knowledge of the content, understand the place of man in his/her environment in totality and possess the skills to effectively identify the impact of man as a catalyst of change in the environment. The above premise supports the position of Joyce, Weil and Calhoun (2004) cited in Obadiora (2009) that teachers should be knowledgeable about the subject matter and be committed to making decision that involves the use of a variety of instructional strategies and approaches appropriate to the diverse needs of students. Also, Brown (2004) has argued that students learn with varying degrees of success, through reading, memorizing, thinking, writing, note-taking in lectures, observing, learning to and talking with others and by doing things. In addition, they may learn in structured situations such as lectures, courses or learning packages. He argued further that the ways students learn could only be accounted for through effective and well-planned methods and use of instructional materials.

Suggestions

Based on the outcomes of this study, it was recommended that tertiary institutions offering Social Studies should dedicate more time to the teaching of the methods and their applications in the classroom setting. Apart from the period set aside for teaching practice and micro-teaching, students' participation should be encouraged.

Social Studies teachers in the service should be exposed to constant training and re-training to update their knowledge in teaching methods. This is necessary because of the dynamic nature of the subject.

Social Studies teachers should embark on the writing and publication of textbooks that would assist in the teaching of Social Studies.

Empirical studies should be conducted by Social Studies experts on the efficacy of the methodologies. These studies are necessary to validate the filling of the existing knowledge gap in the effectiveness of each of the methodologies.

Conclusion

This study explored the place of methodologies in teaching of qualitative Social Studies in Nigeria. It was concluded that many methods were available for Social Studies teachers and in order to benefit from them, they should have knowledge, skills and abilities that come from education. It was further concluded that no teaching method was the best. All of them were effective in their own ways. The widening scope of Social Studies required constant research into its teaching methodologies.

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